

1 **HPV E5 control of Kank1/Kank4.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 The functions of the E5 gene of human papillomavirus remain incompletely defined. Some have described
7 partial transforming potential for E5 but only E6 and E7 are known to induce transformation through
8 inactivation of p53 and Rb1. We used transcriptomics here, measuring total transcription by
9 RNA-sequencing following artificial expression of E5 to identify putative E5 network targets and interaction
10 partners in human cells. We describe here activation of *Kank1* and *Kank4* by the E5 protein of HPV16 and
11 HPV84.

12 Citations

13 1. DiMaio, D. and Mattoon, D., 2001. Mechanisms of cell transformation by papillomavirus E5
14 proteins. *Oncogene*, 20(54), pp.7866-7873.

15 2. Bouchet, B.P., Gough, R.E., Ammon, Y.C., van de Willige, D., Post, H., Jacquemet, G., Altelaar,
16 A.M., Heck, A.J., Goult, B.T. and Akhmanova, A., 2016. Talin-KANK1 interaction controls the recruitment
17 of cortical microtubule stabilizing complexes to focal adhesions. *Elife*, 5, p.e18124.

18 GSE228187